

PURINE METABOLISM

- **Green:** Unique in *Serratia*
- **Pink:** Unique in *Rickettsiella*
- **Olive:** Encoded by both *Serratia* & *Rickettsiella*

PYRUVATE METABOLISM

- **Green:** Unique in *Serratia*
- **Pink:** Unique in *Rickettsiella*
- **Olive:** Encoded by both *Serratia* & *Rickettsiella*

CITRATE CYCLE (TCA CYCLE)

- **Green:** Unique in *Serratia*
- **Pink:** Unique in *Rickettsiella*
- **Olive:** Encoded by both *Serratia* & *Rickettsiella*

GLYCINE, SERINE AND THREONINE METABOLISM

- **Green:** Unique in *Serratia*
- **Pink:** Unique in *Rickettsiella*
- **Olive:** Encoded by both *Serratia* & *Rickettsiella*

VITAMIN B 6 METABOLISM

- **Green:** Unique in *Serratia*
- **Pink:** Unique in *Rickettsiella*
- **Olive:** Encoded by both *Serratia* & *Rickettsiella*

BIOTIN METABOLISM

- **Green:** Unique in *Serratia*
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- **Olive:** Encoded by both *Serratia* & *Rickettsiella*

RIBOFLAVIN METABOLISM

- **Green:** Unique in *Serratia*
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ARGININE BIOSYNTHESIS

- **Green:** Unique in *Serratia*
- **Pink:** Unique in *Rickettsiella*
- **Olive:** Encoded by both *Serratia* & *Rickettsiella*